

ISic4415

Epitaph for Krimma, child of Aunakos

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

sandstone

Object

plinth

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Autopsy

Metcalfe 2016 visited site

Last Change

2020-05-27 - Jonathan Prag created the file from template and publications

Place of origin (ancient)

Abacaenum

Place of origin (modern)

near Tripi

Provenance

Tomb 69/70 of the necropolis in contrada Cardusa , where it remains in situ

Coordinates

38.065190, 15.114380

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Tripi, Necropoli di Abakainon

Physical Description

Plinth (support for a stele) with mouldings top and bottom, of the local sandstone; the upper moulding is damaged, principally at the corners. The plinth is the left one of a pair mounted on a single base, classified as an epitombion of type C.

Dimensions

Height 32 cm

Width 60 cm

Depth 67 cm

Layout

Single line of greek letters approximately centred on the face of the plinth

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Small simple letters. Kappa has short equal arms, attached to the vertical; rho has small closed eye; mu has slanting first and final strokes, with the mid-strokes joining as a curve and only descending half-way; alpha is broad with straight bar, in one case slightly curved with the apex extending at the top; nu has shorter right vertical joining the diagonal above the line; omicron is small and mid-line.

Letter heights:

Line 1: 30 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: NA mm

Text

1. Κριμμα Αυνακου

Apparatus

text of Sofia 2018

Translation (en)

Krimma, child of Aunakos

Commentary

The name Κριμμα lacks parallels (although note Κριμματίων [<http://www.lgpn.ox.ac.uk/id/V3b-13184>] at Pythion in northern Greece, and is most likely an indigenous name; the same is true for Αυνακος. This plinth is one of a pair on a single base - a type attested several times in this necropolis - and the second plinth (ISic4416 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic4416>]) is also inscribed and appears also to bear the name Αυνακος in the genitive as its second element, suggesting that the tomb is a double one for siblings. The same situation seems to be attested in the case of ISic4417 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic4417>] / ISic4418 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic4418>] . The first name here appears to be in the nominative (which has a parallel in ISic1208 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic1208>]), rather than the more commonly found genitive in this necropolis.

Digital identifiers:

Bibliography

- Bacci, G.M., Coppolino, P. 2009. La Necropoli di Abakainon: primi dati. Messina. At 28 fig.15 (and ref on p.113)
- Sofia, G. 2018. Nuove iscrizioni funerarie dalla necropoli di Abakainon. *Zeitschrift für Papyrologie und Epigraphik*. 206: 103-112. At 107 no.5 and fig.6

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